

Methodology for Cleaning, Quality, and Normalization of Vegetation Index Data Derived from Sentinel 2

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Abstract

This paper proposes a methodology for preprocessing, cleaning, and normalizing vegetation indices derived from Sentinel-2 remote sensing data (satellites 2A and 2B), with an initial focus on the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). However, the methodology can be easily adapted to other vegetation indices that can be generated from these sensors. The method describes steps for extracting and cropping areas of interest, removing invalid data via quality assurance (QA) bands, discarding outliers based on user-provided parameters, and using anomaly detection algorithms, particularly the *Local Outlier Factor* (LOF), to produce post-processed data suitable for precision agriculture analysis and phenological modeling. Preliminary results indicate that the proposed workflow removes common noise such as cloud cover and shadows, as well as non-physical or inconsistent NDVI values, enabling more robust and reliable analyses.

1 Introduction

Satellite remote sensing has revolutionized the analysis of agricultural areas, allowing for the extraction of various vegetation indices that aid in crop monitoring, pest detection, water stress assessment, and other relevant applications. Among these indices, NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) is one of the most used due to its simplicity and robustness in detecting vegetation cover.

However, anomalous values (or outliers) in NDVI can occur due to various factors such as clouds, cloud shadows, aerosols, lighting conditions, and calibration errors. These anomalies can significantly compromise temporal and spatial analyses, leading to inaccurate or inconsistent interpretations.

Thus, this paper presents a methodology for cleaning and homogenizing (which we will call *post-processed NDVI*) NDVI values from Sentinel-2A and 2B. Although we use NDVI as the main example, the described techniques are applicable to other vegetation indices derived from the same bands (e.g., EVI, SAVI, etc.), by simply adapting the calculation functions and possible expected physical limits.

2 Materials and Methods

In this section, we describe in detail the workflow steps, using Python and the `xarray` library for image manipulation. The following topics will be covered:

1. **Source of Sentinel 2A and 2B data, with the area of interest (crop).**
2. **Initial focus on the NDVI index (*raw NDVI*).**
3. **Use of the `xarray` library to handle images.**
4. **Generation of general statistics of raw NDVI.**
5. **Removal of invalid data via quality assurance (QA) bands.**
6. **Refinement of the crop, discarding cloud areas and other artifacts.**
7. **Removal of outliers based on parameters provided by the user.**
8. **Application of LOF (*Local Outlier Factor*), with a focal window defined in meters.**
9. **Generation of *post-processed NDVI*.**
10. **Processing of general statistics of *post-processed NDVI*.**

2.1 Acquisition of Sentinel-2 Data and Pre-processing

Sentinel-2A and 2B data can be downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub or any other repository providing these images. For this work, it is assumed that the user already has the images in a compatible format (e.g., SAFE or GeoTIFF) and, optionally, already reprojected to the appropriate spatial reference.

2.2 Calculation of Raw NDVI (NDVI raw)

NDVI is generally calculated by the following expression:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}}$$

In Sentinel-2 images, the commonly used *Red* band is B4 (around 665 nm) and the *NIR* band is B8 (around 842 nm). Assuming we have these bands opened in Python via `xarray`, the code for calculating NDVI (*raw NDVI*) could be:

```
1 import xarray as xr
2
3 # Example of opening data in xarray (GeoTIFF or NetCDF):
4 ds = xr.open_dataset("sentinel2_bands.nc")
5
6 # Assuming the dataset has variables "B4" and "B8"
7 red = ds['B4']
8 nir = ds['B8']
9
```

```

10 # Calculation of NDVI
11 ndvi_raw = (nir - red) / (nir + red)
12
13 # We can save it in a DataArray or to disk:
14 ndvi_raw.name = "NDVI_raw"
15 ndvi_raw.to_netcdf("ndvi_raw.nc")

```

2.2.1 General Statistics of Raw NDVI

Before any cleaning, it is interesting to generate statistics like *minimum*, *maximum*, *mean*, *median*, *standard deviation*, or histogram. This allows evaluating the data's state, identifying plausible physical ranges, and data clearly outside the curve. For example:

```

1 import numpy as np
2
3 min_val = ndvi_raw.min().values
4 max_val = ndvi_raw.max().values
5 mean_val = ndvi_raw.mean().values
6 std_val = ndvi_raw.std().values
7
8 print("Min NDVI Raw:", min_val)
9 print("Max NDVI Raw:", max_val)
10 print("Mean NDVI Raw:", mean_val)
11 print("Std NDVI Raw:", std_val)

```

2.3 Removal of Invalid Data via QA Bands

Sentinel-2 provides quality assurance bands (*QA bands*) or *mask layers* that indicate the presence of clouds, cloud shadows, snow, water, etc. We use these bands to filter out pixels that do not reliably represent vegetation. For example:

- **Cloud Mask** (cloud filter).
- **Snow Mask** (snow filter, if present).
- **Cirrus Mask** (high-level clouds).

Depending on the Sentinel-2 product, there might be different masking strategies. In Python, a typical process would be:

```

1 qa_mask = ds['QA_band'] # Example: a band with bits indicating clouds
2
3 # Assuming QA_band == 1 indicates a valid pixel, and 0 indicates an
  #   invalid pixel:
4 valid_mask = (qa_mask == 1)
5
6 # Applying the mask to raw NDVI:
7 ndvi_raw_masked = ndvi_raw.where(valid_mask, drop=False)

```

Then, we can generate general statistics again, but only for valid pixels (without clouds, shadows, etc.).

2.4 Refining the Crop Based on the QA Mask

If an additional crop is needed, for example, to remove edge areas or large cloud patches, we can apply clipping operations in `xarray` using the area of interest (e.g., represented in `GeoPandas`):

```
1 import geopandas as gpd
2 from rasterio import features
3
4 # Load the area of interest
5 gdf = gpd.read_file("area_of_interest.shp")
6
7 # Option: convert the polygon to a raster mask and apply in xarray
8 # ...
```

The idea is to ensure only the agricultural area of interest, free from invalid pixels, remains for subsequent analyses.

2.5 Removal of Maximum and Minimum Outliers Based on User Parameters

After eliminating unreliable values through QA, there can still be physically impossible NDVI values (e.g., $\text{NDVI} < -1$ or $\text{NDVI} > 1$, depending on calibration errors, saturation, etc.). Additionally, the user might want to automatically remove pixels exceeding certain percentiles (e.g., below the 1st or above the 99th percentile). This process can be done with a simple clip:

```
1 user_min = -0.2 # Example of minimum limit
2 user_max = 1.0 # Example of maximum limit
3
4 ndvi_clipped = ndvi_raw_masked.clip(min=user_min, max=user_max)
```

2.6 Application of LOF (Local Outlier Factor) with Focal Window

For a more refined detection of spatial outliers, we apply the *Local Outlier Factor* (LOF). LOF considers the density of points (pixels) relative to the nearest neighbors, marking as outliers those whose local density is very different from their neighbors.

For raster data, we need to pay attention to dataset size. One option is to convert the `xarray` into a list of coordinates (x, y) + NDVI value for each pixel, then apply LOF. Below is a conceptual example:

```
1 import numpy as np
2 from sklearn.neighbors import LocalOutlierFactor
3
4 # Convert DataArray to coordinates (x, y, ndvi)
5 da = ndvi_clipped.fillna(-9999) # replace NaN
6 coords_ndvi = []
7 for i in range(da.shape[0]):
8     for j in range(da.shape[1]):
9         value = da.values[i,j]
10        if value != -9999:
```

```

11         coords_ndvi.append([i, j, value])
12
13 coords_ndvi = np.array(coords_ndvi)
14
15 # Apply LOF
16 lof = LocalOutlierFactor(n_neighbors=20, contamination=0.01)
17 outlier_labels = lof.fit_predict(coords_ndvi)
18
19 # -1 -> outlier, 1 -> normal
20 outlier_mask = (outlier_labels == -1)

```

The parameters `n_neighbors` (number of neighbors) and `contamination` (fraction of points to be marked as outliers) can be adjusted. We could also use distance in *meters* instead of neighbor count if the data is in a projected coordinate reference system (e.g., UTM). In that case, we would need to calculate Euclidean distances in meters between pixels (using (x_{utm}, y_{utm}) instead of indices (i, j)).

2.7 Generation of *Post-processed NDVI*

Once outliers are identified, we can replace them with a spatially interpolated value (e.g., using the median of the k nearest non-anomalous neighbors) or simply mark them as *NaN* for later analysis. In Python, we could:

```

1 ndvi_postproc = ndvi_clipped.copy()
2
3 # For each pixel detected as an outlier, we put NaN (or interpolate)
4 outlier_indices = np.where(outlier_mask)[0] # indices in the
        coords_ndvi list
5
6 for idx in outlier_indices:
7     i, j, _ = coords_ndvi[idx]
8     ndvi_postproc.values[int(i), int(j)] = np.nan
9
10 # Or we could interpolate, depending on the defined strategy

```

Finally, we save the result to disk:

```

1 ndvi_postproc.name = "ndvi_postproc"
2 ndvi_postproc.to_netcdf("ndvi_postproc.nc")

```

2.8 General Statistics of *Post-processed NDVI*

Lastly, we calculate statistics again to check for improvement in data quality, observing if there was a reduction in extreme values:

```

1 min_val_h = ndvi_postproc.min().values
2 max_val_h = ndvi_postproc.max().values
3 mean_val_h = ndvi_postproc.mean().values
4 std_val_h = ndvi_postproc.std().values
5
6 print("Min NDVI Post-processed:", min_val_h)
7 print("Max NDVI Post-processed:", max_val_h)
8 print("Mean NDVI Post-processed:", mean_val_h)
9 print("Std NDVI Post-processed:", std_val_h)

```

3 Results and Discussion

The proposed methodology allows for the systematic removal of common issues in remote sensing data for agriculture. The results of the *post-processed NDVI* tend to show greater statistical consistency, with a significant reduction in standard deviation and the elimination of values outside the expected physical range.

The application of LOF has proven effective in detecting point regions with discrepant values, often related to noise (thin clouds, construction materials, unmasked water bodies, etc.). However, caution is needed at crop edges or land-use transition areas to avoid eliminating real variations. Thus, calibration of the parameters `n_neighbors` and `contamination` in LOF is crucial, as is defining minimum and maximum NDVI thresholds.

Despite the initial focus being NDVI, the entire strategy here can be extended to other vegetation indices (e.g., EVI, SAVI, NDRE, etc.), simply by changing the calculation method of the index and the physical validity thresholds.

4 Conclusions

This paper has presented a **complete methodology for cleaning, quality, and normalization of vegetation index data** derived from Sentinel-2, exemplified with NDVI. The main steps include:

1. Extraction of raw NDVI (*NDVI raw*) from Red and NIR bands.
2. Generation of initial statistics.
3. Application of quality masks (QA) to remove obviously invalid data, like clouds and cloud shadows.
4. Specific cropping of the study area.
5. Removal of minimum and maximum outliers based on user parameters.
6. Use of the *Local Outlier Factor* (LOF) for advanced spatial anomaly detection.
7. Production of a *post-processed NDVI*, free from spurious values.
8. Generation of final statistics for quality improvement verification.

The results show that the *post-processed NDVI* is much more suitable for subsequent analyses, such as phenological development tracking and agricultural productivity estimates. For large-scale applications, computational efficiency can be optimized through sampling, block processing, or distributed computing.

References

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